

THE ROLE OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT IN ACHIEVING STRATEGIC VISION IN AFGHANISTAN TELECOM COMPANIES

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Abstract

Telecommunication has been immensely growing in the last few years. Knowledge has long been recognized as an important thing for living. Therefore, managing knowledge in an organization has been interesting since it can provide a competitive advantage in the complex world. In the globalization, one has to confront with uncertainty of business environment, high competitiveness, and jumping from production-based to knowledge-based economy. Thus, knowledge management becomes acceptable as a competitive weapon in this situation. While organizations are interested in knowledge management to increase their competitiveness sustainably, there is a need to study the critical success factors for KM implementation. These will ensure that important issues, activities, and practices are paid attention during design or implementation of KM. 50Due to a subjective manner of KM, there is no common or standard ways in a KM practice. KM is however, related to many parts, people in an organization that make managing knowledge quite complex. To make it more confident to design and implement KM in the right way, many issues should be addressed that allows implementers to pay attention to them.

Keywords: Telecom Companies, Afghanistan, Knowledge Management

Introduction

The following definition of knowledge management (KM) was developed by the Gartner Group a few years after the Davenport definition and is now the one that is most frequently quoted (Duhon, 1998): "A discipline called knowledge management encourages an integrated method for locating, analysing, storing, retrieving, and sharing all of an organization's information assets. Databases, records, regulations, procedures, and hitherto untapped knowledge and experience in certain employees are a few examples of these assets." This definition's one genuine flaw is that it, too, only refers to an organization's own information and knowledge assets. As this expansion was added early on, KM has come to contain all pertinent information assets from all relevant sources. But, take note of the scope that being called a "discipline" for KM implies.

Since individuals are the source of knowledge, speaking with an expert is frequently the greatest approach to gain the expertise you require. Finding the appropriate expert with the information you require, however, can be challenging, especially if, for example, the expert is located overseas. An expertise locator system's primary purpose is to locate and identify people who have knowledge in a specific field inside an organisation. Expertise location systems are the name given to these systems in modern times.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The review of literature is based on the concept of KM practices that help create a strategic vision in companies.

Al-jaafreh, Amani&Fayoumi, Amjad (2017) in their study stated that the Telecom companies face a fierce competition from innovation based start-up companies, particularly those that are using internet networks to offer communication services through the voice and video over internet protocol (VoIP &PVoIP) technologies. More than 10 years have passed from the time the internet and VoIP were widely used, but still, telecom companies are having a great deal of business success through offering a wide spectrum of services, products, deals, and packages to consumers using both B2C and B2B models. The future landscape of how telecom companies will evolve in the market is still not clear, particularly with the increase of aggressive competition from companies that are technology- innovative and starting to deliver new forms of ubiquitous communication technology and services. Understanding why and how telecom companies innovate in the market is very crucial in order to predict the future of this business sector. In this paper, we argue that telecom companies are utilizing their capabilities that have a significantly important role in fostering innovation, namely information technology (IT) capability and knowledge management (KM) capability. IT capabilities have changed dramatically in the last few years with the introduction of intelligent systems, big data analytics, the Internet of Things and the wide use of mobile apps and sensors. It is not clear how these technologies play a role in telecom companies' innovation and it is not clear whether IT impacts innovation directly or if KM capability has a mediation role in utilising technology to support innovation. This paper is a position paper to establish grounds for understanding how telecom companies innovate, and in particular how IT and KM capabilities influence innovation. We outline the methodology of this investigation as a

qualitative study with stakeholders from multiple telecom companies and we expect at the end of the study to be able to offer a holistic view on the way these companies innovate in regard to their products and services. We aim at providing a cross case studies comparison towards a prediction of the future of the telecom business sector.

Aref Hajir, Jinan &Obeidat, Bader & Al-dalahmeh, Mahmoud &Masa'deh, Ra'ed. (2015) stated that the aim of the research is to explore the role of Knowledge Management (KM) infrastructure (Organizational culture, Organizational structure, human resource, information technology, and physical environment) in enhancing innovation at mobile telecommunication companies.

Danial Hassan (2014) stated Employee turnover had become a serious problem in knowledge-intensive industries such as telecommunications, where the resulting knowledge loss affects process safety and quality. This study examined knowledge management practices in Pakistan's telecom sector and argued that the impact of knowledge loss could be mitigated through knowledge management. Based on a structured questionnaire administered online to a sample of telecom operators in Pakistan, the results indicated the absence of knowledge management as a strategic response to knowledge loss. Nonetheless, the presence of a young, educated workforce, a strong cooperative culture, and sound ICT provision could be leveraged to build successful knowledge management systems in this sector.

HamdanSalimAlawamleh and Mohammad AbdalraheemKloub (2013) stated that the aim of this study was to investigate the impact of organizational structure on knowledge management and applications (Knowledge acquisition, knowledge storage, dissemination of knowledge, the use of knowledge). The study recommends that design of appropriate organizational structures, which is pushing for

more production and application of knowledge as a prerequisite for the survival and success.

Shannak, Rifat&Masa'deh, Ra'ed&Akour, Mohammed (2012) mentioned that the purpose of the paper is to discuss the main aspects of Knowledge Management Strategy building in the organizations. The paper discusses the meaning of KM strategy, the methods used to build the strategy, how researchers see the approaches to pursuing an effective KM Strategy in organizations, and what are the new trends in strategy building. Earlier and recent scholars (e.g. Mintzberg, 1979; Barney and Hesterly, 2010; Acur et al., 2012) emphasized that strategy building could be seen as a way to achieve organizational goals and objectives, and therefore achieving the organizational vision in order to sustain competitive advantage. Most studies do not explicitly describe how Knowledge Management (KM) Strategy is formulated and aligned with business strategies (Lee and Chin, 2012). It is generally acknowledged by experts in the area that KM strategies must be aligned with the business vision; they must reflect why knowledge is important; knowledge managers must practise what they preach, and it must provide channels for discussion and allow for the flow of ideas. The consequences of not perceiving are dire and will certainly make impossible to realize the business value of knowledge management for the organization.

Seyede Zahra Erfani, BabakAkhgar and FarzadRamin (2010) stated that in this turbulent business environment of global recession and knowledge economic ages along with the unceasing gravity of knowledge, knowledge management already became the source to improve Industry competitive ability. This study attempted to propose a model for KMI (Knowledge Management implementation), in the Mobile telecommunication industry. In presenting the model for Mobile telecommunication industry which the authors called it; Erfaniet *al.*, KMI model; they followed KM (Knowledge Management) models and took

advantage of Deming Cycle model and control project models, they also considered Critical Success Factors (CSFs) and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) of core process in order to identify valuable knowledge. Erfaniet *al.*, KMI model consists of initiation, planning, executing, monitoring, controlling and closing phases. Since knowledge management audit is an important step of KMI, in the first Phase KM cycle would be assessed in the organization under study; in this research KM in the Mobile Telephone Switching Office (MTSO) was assessed based on Jashapara's KM cycle; latter includes four loops; knowledge creation, knowledge organization, knowledge sharing and knowledge leverage. In the second phase of the model the valuable knowledge for the company under study would be identified, in the third phase the procedures for managing the valuable knowledge would be done, in the fourth phase the KM statues and it's effect on some productivity keys would be evaluated and in the last phase all the processes would be documented. This paper suggests that by implementing this model organization is able to increase their productivity index and be prosperous in KM. In order to verify and validate the performed research, Erfaniet *al.*, KMI model has been accomplished in the Mobile Telephone Switching Office and other companies, positive and acceptable results were obtained and organizations total factor productivity increase was achieved which was appreciated by the organization, for km assessment in the first phase nd after execution phase, Qualitative method through direct data collection mechanism was used; questioners were delivered and the staffs were interviewed as well the data were analyzed through SPSS software. In identifying CSFs and KPIs; Multi Attribute Group Decision Making (MAGDM) techniques was used. The obtained results indicated that there was improvement in the creating, sharing, organizing and utilizing knowledge and process efficiency index were improved.

Edwards, John, Hall M.J. and Shaw, Duncan (2005) in their paper made a case for taking a systems view of knowledge management within health-care provision, concentrating on the emergency care process in the UK National Health Service. It drew upon research in two case study organizations (a hospital and an ambulance service). The case-study organizations appear to be approaching knowledge (and information) management in a somewhat fragmented way. They were trying to think more holistically, but (perhaps) because of the ways their organizations and their work were structured, they could not 'see' the whole of the care process. The paper explored the complexity of knowledge management in emergency health care and drew the distinction for knowledge management between managing local and operational knowledge, and global and clinical knowledge.

Joseph M. Firestone, Mark W. McElroy (2005) give the best and simple definition that KM is the set of processes that seeks to change the organization's present pattern of knowledge processing to enhance it and its outcomes.

KM is crucial to all or any styles of trades which might facilitate the organizations to think about how to capture the tenant information within the organization. Mostly in telecommunication sector throughout the world, a large number of data staff has been hired to perform the schedule operation of the organization, it is vital for them to speak and share their knowledge. Therefore, telecom corporations today are willing to invest and capture the maximum amount of knowledge as attainable from their most experienced staff. Some massive telecommunications service provider begins to form a senior-level management position in their organization to make sure that KM operates effectively [Kogut, B. & Zander, U. (1992), Lewis-Chan, Betsy (1998)].

According to Strouse, Karen G. (2001) some reputable telecom corporations like British Telecom, AT & T, and Deutsche Telekom have created chief information officer positions in

their organization., it demonstrates the fact that the telecommunications industry believe that intellectual assets have worth. The following numerous factors identified by Strouse, Karen G. (2001) which are important for an effective KM systems in telecommunication sector.

- i. IT supports needs to be adequate in both scale and communications response time.
- ii. Database should include user-friendly search capabilities.
- iii. Tools in the search engine need to pinpoint the proper information when requested.
- iv. Processes need to support the facilitation of information retrieval and must be in place to assist in the creation of new information.
- v. System performance metrics should be maintained in order to help to determine the criteria for new data to enter the system.
- vi. Type of data to be available must pass tests defined in the design phase, it should be limited to information that will increase the performance of employees or improve the customer's experience.
- vii. Effective incentives and supportive core values should be encouraged to the most expert employees to share their knowledge.

People conjointly perpetually argue that the advantages of information management systems seem to be too theoretical to measure; the subsequent is an example of returns from implementing KM in telecommunication trade [Dykeman, J.B. (1998)]. Quantification of advantages is most blatant in client service sectors like sales and client support department for instance, a client service center may use a KM system to assist service representatives to spot the supply of issues by listing troubleshooting measures that were successful within the past. Therefore, additional issues are resolved with one decision in client service centers [Auckland, Marc. (1999)]. Telecommunications service suppliers have

used KM systems to extend their sales productivity. Sales representatives tend to concentrate on those services sold successfully in past. KM systems will assist to extend sales services by providing data to the sales representative in smaller amount. [Y. Malhotra (1998), Lisa Minogue-White (2006) and K. Wiig (1997)].

The progressive development made in ontologies to represent knowledge. The aim of developing ontologies is to provide flexibility and richness in KM. To develop semantics KM, researchers are paying attention to contribute significantly in developing theoretical and practical understanding of ontologies [D. Coleman (1998) and N.J. Davies (2000)].

The authors describe a research project to deploy knowledge networks in a high technology company. The aim of implementing this project was to make deep understanding of network setup and show to be sustained. In this paper two different projects are discussed with two different level of maturity and some tentative modules were analyzed as follows [W.J. Orlikowski (2002) and M. Schönström (2005)].

- To categorize and support knowledge activists.
- Apply strategic agenda to put knowledge networks.
- Major organizational changes may be vulnerable to formal networks.
- To build and understand that how formal networks can coincide with line organization.

Today, knowledge is the most important strategic resource, while learning is a more important strategic capability for business organizations, as many managers believe that the advantages will be achieved strategically possess more knowledge than owned competitors, even though they are not able to clearly define the link between knowledge and strategy. The knowledge is the most important resource and it is essential for organizations attachment for the activities of the organization

in making smart decisions, forecasting, design, planning, diagnosis and all the provisions intuitive (Collis & Hussey, 2003). Knowledge depend on the data and information that had been organized and processed to be able to connect the understanding, experience, accumulated learning and experience when applied to the ongoing problem or activity (Trubanet. Al., 1999). The knowledge resource investment and strategic commodity through the employment of all the possibilities of information and communication technologies that have become one of the most growing sectors, (Pizan, 2006). Yassin (2006) explains that the knowledge is a combination of concepts and ideas, rules and procedures.

The knowledge as a systematic experiments and test hypotheses which refers to the objective and explanatory models to understand the surrounding, (Stromquist, 2000), Anzi (2001) mentioned that the information for customers, professional data base, and models for analysis and successful solutions to deal with problems as well as specialized knowledge of the organization, Sarvary (1999) attempted to show the redundant information causal relationships that help feeling this information, knowledge is the group meanings and concepts, beliefs and perceptions of mind to answer questions individual saturated ambitions, and realized his creations what he wants to know (Wit & Meyer, 1998). Knowledge is an individual's ability to recognize and distinguish things "or" the ability possessed by the individual and stored in his mind form cognitive maps (Mustafa, 1998), it is the ability to translate information into the performance to achieve a specific task, or find a specific thing, which is only available in human minds and intellectual skills (Bellinger, 2003), relations models of data and information with other models. Daft (2003) show that knowledge is different from the data and information, because the human factor in knowledge constitutes a key element books contain a collection of information that becomes knowledge when absorbed into our individual

use, and see if knowledge is the conclusion which draws information correlated with other information and views.

Wenig (1996) indicates that knowledge management includes a range of activities that focus on gaining organizational knowledge from their own experience and the experience of others, including the application wise to know in order to achieve the organization's mission, and these activities are being implemented through the integration of technology and organizational structure and strategies, organization-backed knowledge of the current and the production of new knowledge. Hirsch and Levin (1999) show that knowledge management is an umbrella framework of the organization, these researchers emphasize that the management of knowledge beyond being a mere information or data. That there is no standard definition of one of the concept of knowledge management, is that there are two tracks of activities and efforts that interested in the concept of knowledge management, and these two tracks: the first track is the path information (Information Track): In this path seen that knowledge management is the same information management, the owners of this is seen the path to knowledge as the information being processed information systems. The second path is the path of persons.

According to this path, the express knowledge about the processes that reflected her skill sets dynamic and complex and somewhat variable (Svieby,2000). Knowledge management is the process whereby the extraction and intellectual capital investment your organization, in order to reach decisions efficient and effective innovative in order to give (Chou Yeh,2005) processes that help organizations to share knowledge, generated, organize, store, and apply them, and work to transform knowledge as contained in the (data, information and trends and capabilities) into products and services and use the outputs of knowledge management in the formulation of learning processes, solving problems and achieving a

learning organization (Badr,2010). Knowledge management is an institutional process aimed at coordination and integration of operations data processing and information technologies, human resources and factors surrounding the institution (Alaklabe,2008). Singh (2008) returning the onset of knowledge management to without Marchand in the beginning of the eighties of the last century, as the final stage of the assumptions relating to the development of information systems.

As Drucker predicted that the work would be based on the model of knowledge and that the organizations will consist of know-makers directing their performance through feedback to colleagues and customers. Some due to knowledge management (1985) when Hewlett Packard company have been applied it, but in this period was not convinced many knowledge management and its impact on business, so that Wall Street "the largest capital market in the world," ignoring the knowledge management initially, especially attempts to determine the monetary value of knowledge, although it has been cared by then, as witnessed eighties also development of knowledge management systems that rely on the work performed in artificial intelligence systems and expertise, and this presents concepts such as knowledge acquisition or acquisitions acquisition.

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Every organization must have its own knowledge management (KM) vision, in line with its business or organizational strategic priorities. A KM vision helps everybody in the organization share the understanding of why the organization needs KM, and the strategic nature of the KM program. The following can be considered as a KM vision statement:

"Knowledge management (KM) is an enabler to achieve organization's strategic objectives better and faster, by making the right knowledge available to the right person at the

right time, and by eliminating ‘reinvention of the wheel.’ KM seeks to facilitate the flow of knowledge from where it resides to where it’s required—that is, where it can be applied or used to achieve an organization’s objectives. KM also seeks to create permanent, reusable “organizational knowledge,” as opposed to individual knowledge that is lost to the organization when the person leaves. This can be achieved by developing an integrated set of KM processes, roles, systems, and behavioral interventions aimed at achieving the company’s vision and objectives. The organization’s leadership plays the most critical role in a strategic KM program, since it must provide the KM vision and direction. A KM governance body consisting of cross-functional and/or cross-departmental leaders must be created in a company. Members of the governance body should be serious about the KM program, expect effective results, get involved, and spend the necessary amount of time required to provide direction to ensure that the organization gets results from KM.

Methodology of the Study:

Most of these studies in the past were based on the analytical descriptive-questionnaire approach as a main tool for collecting data. The current study is descriptive and analytical as it takes the views of managers and employees or their representatives in the administrations of telecommunications companies.

The study collected data from relevant secondary sources such as articles published in technical and management journals and periodicals. Internet based articles, newspapers and other blogs etc., may provide further insights, forming part of the secondary data source that would give insights and data in achieving a Strategic Vision in Afghanistanian Telecom Companies. are equipped with bundle of competent strategies.

1. The telecom companies in Afghanistan are considered to have dynamic oligopoly.

2. The telecom companies in Afghanistan have skilled human resources that work towards effective knowledge management.
3. The telecom companies in Afghanistan due to knowledge management are capable of implementing emergent strategic direction.

1.4.5 Conceptual Framework of the study

2.2 Research Gaps:

Research gaps identified from previous studies: Most previous studies aimed at the need to investigate the effects of the current study variables, but the previous studies did not address the issue of the impact between knowledge management and the environment with specific focus on strategy. The studies in the past have covered some of the issues relating to the subject of the study without providing any detailed view of the dimensions of comprehensive knowledge management and its impact on the subject of the strategic

environment which clearly takes precedence over that.

3.1 Research Questions

The following questions have been raised:

1. What is the role of innovation in defining strategic vision in telecommunications companies in Afghanistan?
2. What is the role of acquiring knowledge in formulating the strategic vision in the telecommunications companies in Afghanistan?
3. What is the role of knowledge organization in formulating strategic vision in the telecommunications companies in Afghanistan?
4. What is the role of knowledge distribution in the formulation of strategic vision in telecommunications companies in Afghanistan?
5. What is the role of using knowledge in achieving a strategic vision in telecommunications companies in Afghanistan?

3.2 Research Objectives

The study focuses on the following objectives:

1. To understand the concept of Knowledge Management and its practices.
2. To understand the role of Knowledge Management in building a strategic vision in companies.
3. To study the profile of Telecom companies situated in Afghanistan.
4. To analyse whether KM is playing a role in achieving a Strategic Vision in Afghanistanian Telecom companies.
5. To establish whether top management support affects KM implementation in Telecom companies in Afghanistan.
6. To build a framework for implementation of effective Knowledge Management practices in Telecom companies in Afghanistan that helps enable a strategic vision.

Scope of the study

The study focuses on ascertaining and analysing the role of KM practices in achieving Strategic Vision in Afghanistan Telecom Companies. As such it makes use of KM practice factors along with related literature in Afghanistan to quantify this study. The study is expected to ascertain the implementation of the said KM practices in achieving Strategic Vision in Afghanistan Telecom Companies. This is a comprehensive study of all Telecom companies in Afghanistan as to give perspective to devise and implement likely operative strategies in Telecom companies in Afghanistan.

Significance of the Study:

This study will help to understand KMS in telecom companies of Afghanistan by presenting empirical and analytical study to expand the existing literature in relation to KM. The study will increase awareness of the importance of KM process and to attempt to project a better understanding of how KM could be approached effectively in telecom companies of Afghanistan. After a thorough study, policy makers and top management in telecommunication industry would be encouraged to apply and implement KMS to improve the skill of the organizations and make them more effective and efficient. The study would improve decision making and provide a strategic vision to the company. Though it is difficult to survey the accuracy of KM practices in creating a strategic vision in telecom companies, a study in order to ascertain the role played by such practices should be conducted. Hence, the present empirical study is taken up under the title **“The Role of Knowledge Management in Achieving Strategic Vision in Afghanistan Telecom Companies.”**

Research Problem:

The specific purpose of the study is to analyze the role played by KM in achieving a strategic

vision in Telecom companies in Afghanistan. Since the telecom companies around the world manage knowledge effectively and consider that it is capable in creating a strategic vision. The major focus will be on how well a strategic vision is achieved by implementing KM with special preference to the telecom companies in Afghanistan.

Limitations of this Research

The study is constrained by physical location as the study is limited to Telecom companies in Afghanistan. The scope of research cannot be made wider by covering all the Telecom companies in the world. The sample size represents the whole country which makes it difficult for the researcher to analyze all the factors desired to be studied. Time constraint is also one of the main limitations of the research. Better results can be obtained if sufficient time is invested in conducting the research.

DISCUSSION

Although the role of top management is important to ensure that KM is aligned with the organization's strategic priorities, it's also important that KM becomes widely accepted, and that employees across the organization participate in knowledge sharing and replication. A KM culture can't be created if it remains an exclusive or elite initiative in which only a few people are involved. It's only by KM becoming a mass movement that the *culture* of knowledge sharing and replication will spread and establish itself in the organization.

The effectiveness of a company's KM in delivering real business results will go up exponentially if standard processes are established for sharing and replication of knowledge. A policy not to leave submission and publication of knowledge in knowledge repositories must be devised. Robust processes must be put in place that makes it mandatory – not optional – to share internal best practices and other internal and external knowledge relevant to top priority measures. Eventually, as

KM maturity increases, these processes will get embedded in regular work processes.

Knowledge management is relatively a new subject and most of its theories, concepts and practices are going through massive changes world over. Therefore Knowledge Management is still in its formative stages. This is exhibited by the numerous definitions that exist about the subject. According to C. Collison and G. Parcell (2005), Knowledge Management is about capturing, creating, distilling, sharing and using know-how. They further state that know-how includes tacit and explicit knowledge. Know-how is used as short hand for Know-what, Know-who, Know-why and Know-when. According to R. Daft (2010) Knowledge Management is the process of systematically gathering knowledge, making it widely available throughout the organization. A utilitarian description of knowledge management is provided by Skyme who states that it is the flow of knowledge that is important (D. Skyme, 1997).

Despite the fact that knowledge management is undergoing the crystallization process, it is well received by many organizations, especially in the developed countries. A survey of 200 large firms in the United States of America revealed that 80% of the corporations had knowledge initiatives (B. France, and S. Kathleen, 2002). This gives an indication of how knowledge management is a vital undertaking by any organization that exists in this century.

Overview of Telecom Sector:

The telecommunications sector is made up of companies that make communication possible on a global scale, whether it is through the phone or the Internet, through airwaves or cables, through wires or wirelessly. These companies created the infrastructure that allows data in words, voice, audio or video to be sent anywhere in the world. The largest companies in the sector are wireless operators, satellite companies, cable companies, and internet service providers.

Evolution of Telecom Sector:

The telecommunications sector evolved from the telegraph, the first mechanical device. It shortened communication from days to hours – much as modern mobile technology shortened the time span of sending large amounts of data from hours to seconds. These shifts are due to technology, and they changed how people live and do business. At one time, telecommunications required physical wires connecting homes and businesses. In contemporary society, technology has gone mobile; digital, wireless technology is becoming the primary form of communication.

The sector's structure has also changed from a few large players to a more decentralized system with decreased regulation and barriers to entry. Major public corporations act as the service providers, while smaller companies sell and service the equipment, such as routers, switches, and infrastructure, which enable this communication. For growth investors, these companies provide the best opportunities for share price appreciation. In contrast, larger companies tend to be havens for conservative, income-focused investors.

Main Factors of the Evolution of the Sector

The evolution of the telecommunications industry in the U.S. centers on five main factors. Wireless Internet is quickly becoming the industry's future, and its popularity is consistently increasing revenue. Also, an expansion of high-speed, fiber-based networks is expected. In addition to these elements, a shortage of airwaves has caused a consolidation within the industry.

The fifth factor is the copious potential for growth. As of 2018, the Federal Communications Commission (FCC) reports that approximately one-fifth of the rural American population still does not have access to broadband networks.

However, the ultimate determination for growth is wireless Internet. This piece of the industry is the anticipated keystone for the continued

global expansion of the telecommunications sector. Furthermore, this industry has experienced a shift in focus from voice calls to video and data. There is an increasing demand for speedier data connectivity, higher resolution, quicker video streaming, and ample multimedia applications.

Key Segments within the Telecommunications Sector:

The telecommunications sector consists of three basic sub-sectors: telecom equipment (the largest), telecom services (next largest) and wireless communication.

The major segments within these sub-sectors include the following:

- Wireless communications
- Communications equipment
- Processing systems and products
- Long-distance carriers
- Domestic telecom services
- Foreign telecom services
- Diversified communication services

The smallest, but fastest-growing, area within the sector is wireless communications, as more and more communications and computing shift to mobile devices. Looking forward, the sector's biggest challenge is to keep up with people's demand for faster connections as they consume and create content, which requires significant capital expenditures. Companies that can meet these needs thrive.

Investing in Telecommunications:

Telecommunications companies are a rarity in the stock market; their shares have, at times, exhibited characteristics of both income and growth stocks. For periods of several years, a company may enjoy its regulatory privileges (like other utilities, telecom firms often are protected from competition by government mandate), and produce reliable, generous

dividend yields (generated by high monthly revenue from its stable customer base). Then, suddenly, technological advances or mergers and acquisitions create uncertainty and leave room for loss – and recovery, with fresh growth.

This makes the telecommunications sector is an attractive option for value investors because it is an integral part of the global economy. Demand for telecommunications services persists regardless of changes in the business cycle. But if a firm hits a slump because of shifts in the industry (like the growing importance of wireless devices), value investors might snap it up, provided its fundamentals remain strong and it proves adept at adapting to change. The telecommunications sector's record in paying and regularly raising dividends makes the waiting period for share prices to improve more enjoyable.

However, all of the three major telecom sectors present a greater risk to investors, with stocks registering anywhere from 7% (for services) to 15% (wireless) to 24% (equipment) more volatility than the broader market. Investors with heavy exposure to telecom can expect stronger-than-average gains during bull markets. When a recession or bear market hits, however, losses from this sector can be severe.

Telecommunications Companies: Big Players

Current industry leaders worldwide can change from year to year. Determining which are the largest depends on whether one looks in terms of total sales numbers or in terms of market capitalization value as well.

Roshan which has only been in business since 2003, has a market cap value of approximately \$ 600 billion due to the growth in the use of cell phones and Internet services in China within the past 15 years.

Afghan Wireless Communication Company (AWCC), which provides wireless and wireline services, in addition to broadband and information services, has a current market capitalization value of approximately \$ 800

billion. It remains attractive as a dividend provider because of its rock-solid financial condition: It is the largest telecom company in the Afghanistan and operates in 34 provinces.

Etisalat etisalat Afghanistan was launched in 2007 after the UAE telecom operator won the license to operate as the fourth mobile services provider in the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan.

The operator rapidly became the fastest-growing telecommunications service provider of the country. etisalat Afghanistan has invested over US\$300 million in the Afghan telecom industry, and it is a wholly owned by etisalat Group. In 2012, etisalat won 3G license in Afghanistan and launched the first 3G services in history of Afghanistan. etisalat shares 60 to 70 mobile towers with government-owned Afghan Telecom, which seeks to grow its five percent market share.

MTN – is a South African multinational mobile telecommunications company, operating in many African and Asian countries. Its head office is in Johannesburg. As of December 2020, MTN recorded 280 million subscribers, making it the 8th largest mobile network operator in the world, and the largest in Africa. Active in over 20 countries, one-third of the company's revenue comes from Nigeria, where it holds about 35% market share.

1.3.6 Outlook for the Telecommunications Sector

Analysts foresee that product innovation and an increase in mergers and acquisitions will only facilitate the continued growth and success of the telecommunications industry. There are many opportunities for investors, and an increase in investors will only serve to benefit the sector further.

The stability of the sector's growth, even during periods of recession, means that it is considered to be a solid defensive investment while maintaining its appeal to growth investors. Even during uncertain and volatile economic times, the steady demand for voice and data services,

along with extensive subscription plans, assures a stable source of revenues for major telecom firms.

Telecommunications has become an increasingly important basic industry, which bodes well for its future prospects and continued growth. The continuing advances in high-speed mobile services and Internet connectivity between devices keep driving innovation and competition within the sector. Much of the industry focus is on providing faster data services, especially in the area of high-resolution video. Essentially, the driving forces are toward quicker and clearer services, increased connectivity and multi-application usage.

Emerging market economies continue to be a boon for the industry, with the growth rate of the cell phone industry in countries such as China and India pushing the abilities of hardware producers to keep up with the level of demand.

In the U.S., analysts are paying close attention to issues surrounding net neutrality as the demand for data and video services continue to increase well into the future. There is still a strong demand for wireless spectrum rights, as indicated by the FCC's Incentive Auction that took place in April 2017, not to mention an increasing trend toward consolidation through mergers and acquisitions.

Telecommunication companies, like other forms of utilities, often operate with stable customer bases that are protected from competition by government mandate. These pseudo-monopolies allow for consistent dividends. However, the dynamic nature of communications has led to mobile and Internet-based phone systems, undermining the demand for traditional landlines. When this happens, telecommunication companies either suffer or adapt, incorporate the new technology and grow rapidly as consumers buy the latest equipment.

1.3.7 Afghanistationian Telecom Sector

Public and private organizations in every industry encounter increased environmental uncertainty and rapid changes in their external environment and the telecom sector is no exception. They are exposed to pressures to improve product or service quality which is presented to the customers in addition to reducing the cost and to compete against other products of high quality.

The strong contribution of telecommunications to the Afghanistan economy is a function of two factors:

1. **Sector Dynamism:** The telecommunications sector is growing, generating in turn direct and indirect jobs. In fact, the operators trigger a significant number of local suppliers, distributions agents, and providers of various services, which enhance the local value added to the economy.

2. **Positive externalities (Spill-over effects):** Telecommunications networks and services result in a more efficient functioning of the economy particularly in terms of:

- Productivity gains in existing sectors (such as tourism, exports, manufacturing) as well as social services, such as education and public administration;
- Innovation incentives, leading to the creation of new businesses in the digital economy (applications, software platforms, local content);
- Integration of isolated regions, leading to further development of economic activities;
- Better coordination among economic agents through improved knowledge of inputs market prices (agriculture), better coordination between economic agents resulting in low transaction costs, enhanced ability to negotiate selling prices; inventory management and delivery tracking;

• Improvement and extension of domestic economic exchanges, as well as at the regional and global scale.

Afghanistan is positioned among countries that have better levered telecommunications for its economic development. In this context, regulators and policy makers need to continue fostering the conditions necessary to stimulate the deployment and modernization of infrastructure, both in terms of fixed and mobile broadband. The telecom service has improved in Afghanistan with the increased use of digital switching equipment, but better access to the telephone system is needed in some rural areas and easier access to pay telephones is needed by the urban public.

Concept of Knowledge

There are many definitions provided for knowledge, and these concepts are summarized in that knowledge is information which can be used and applied. However, some definitions emphasize that knowledge is an integrated set of visions, experiences, facts, beliefs, approaches and techniques that guide individuals, organizations and societies. Knowledge at workplaces refers to the abilities of individuals and organizations to understand, act, and make good decisions (Wiig, 2000, P. 3) (Saleim, 2010, P. 264).

The process of assessing the knowledge situation of a company requires the indexing of the existing intellectual resources through creating a knowledge map which shows the types of knowledge and their relations as well as linking it to the strategy and vice versa in order to bridge the strategic and knowledge gap of the organization against the competitor. The strategic knowledge framework includes (Zack, 1998: 133 - 134):

1. Core knowledge: It is a smaller size and level of knowledge. It should also be available in the organization in order to meet the competition and by which you can know the work rules in the sector. However, it is not given a competitive advantage in the long term.

2. Advanced knowledge: It is the knowledge that enables the organization to acquire competitive capabilities and when it chooses to compete on the basis of knowledge, its focus will be on acquiring further knowledge to achieve superiority over competitors and increasing the quality of knowledge in order to differentiate from its competitors.

3. Innovative knowledge: It is the knowledge that gives the organization the capability to lead the sector. In this case, the differentiation of organization clearly appears compared to competitors, which enables it to change the competition rules in the manner and timing it determines (Al-Kahwi, 2013: 88).

Knowledge Hierarchy

Knowledge can be hierarchically classified and organized beginning with data which is raw facts and inputs; additionally, a set of transformations are carried out to become information which becomes knowledge through the ability to apply them to guide the actions and decisions as follows: (Saleim, 0201, pp. 265-264)

Figure 2: Knowledge Hierarchy

Table 1: The difference among data, information and knowledge.

Table 1Source: Karl, 2000 (Saleim, 2010, P.265

	Data	Information	Knowledge
Content	Events	Trends	Professional Experiences
Shape	Transactions	Patterns	Learning
Information Task	Offer	Processing	Emphasis
Human Element	Note	Evaluation	Experience
Organization Intent	Mechanism	Decision Making	Work, Action and Behavior
Value Test	Assembly and Inventory Data	Sale, uncertainty	New Understanding

Concept of Knowledge Management

Karl Wiig points out that the knowledge management is an organized and specific structure that is developed and updated to maximize knowledge in the enterprise. Becman believes that the knowledge management includes the capability to access professional knowledge and experiences to improve performance and encourage innovation. Overall, the knowledge management is a set of processes and activities used by the organization to acquire, create, transfer, document and use knowledge in the organization (e.g. Saleim, Ashour, 2005a) and (Saleim, 2010, P. 265 - 266).

Strategic Vision

In the meantime, there is an intense competitive between organizations which lead these organizations to the need to develop strategic plans of work along with studying the experience of the past and benefit from it. Therefore, it has become necessary to be aware of modern techniques and benefit from different kinds of knowledge thereby true knowledge of all variables. From here, the strategic vision concept has been introduced

which is one of the strategic planning elements and it became necessary for the organization to define its future direction and seek to achieve it in the reality through a clear strategic and deliberate plan in the sense of how an organization views its future. It is necessary to define the strategic vision of the organization taking into account its potentials and what it can obtain in the future, define its existing opportunities, and predict the future ones. It must be known that the strategic vision depends on the goals of the organization i.e. there must be a clear vision and realistic, true goals and that vision define the place of destination, the ways of achieving to the organization's goals accurately, then the organization would reach its goals.

Knowledge Management and Strategic Vision

The most important element of the organization's success and continuity is putting a clear defined strategic vision. When that vision is formulated and is based on knowledge, information and data, it can achieve and reach to success where it is based on clear and accurate fundamentals. Hence, the importance of knowledge management in formulating the organization's strategic vision and the organization attaining its goals can be

evidenced. The organization that uses knowledge management can build its vision on true information and reality, and achieve what is required from it.

Findings

- There is an association between knowledge management functions (knowledge innovation, knowledge acquisition, knowledge sharing, knowledge storing, knowledge distribution, knowledge usage) and strategic vision in the Afghanistan telecom companies.
- There is no association between knowledge management functions (knowledge innovation, knowledge acquisition, knowledge sharing, knowledge storing, knowledge distribution, knowledge usage) and strategic vision in the Afghanistan telecom companies.
- There is an association between human resources and strategic vision in Afghanistan telecom companies.
- There is no association between human resources and strategic vision in Afghanistan telecom companies.
- There is an association between acquisition of knowledge and strategic vision in the Afghanistan telecom companies.
- There is no association between acquisition of knowledge and strategic vision in the Afghanistan telecom companies.
- There is an association between organizational culture and structure of knowledge and strategic vision in the Afghanistan telecom companies.
- There is no association between organizational culture and structure of knowledge and strategic vision in the Afghanistan telecom companies.
- There is an association between physical environment of organizations and

strategic vision in the Afghanistan telecom companies.

- There is no association between physical environment of organizations and strategic vision in the Afghanistan telecom companies.
- There is a statistically significant difference in the perceptions of employees of the knowledge management functions on the scale of the study due to the Age, Gender, Experience and Career Level.
- There is no statistically significant difference in the perceptions of employees of the knowledge management functions on the scale of the study due to the Age, Gender, Experience and Career Level.
- There is an association between information technology and strategic vision in Afghanistan Telecom companies.
- There is no association between information technology and strategic vision in Afghanistan Telecom companies.

CONCLUSION

A time of unparalleled change has begun in the world, particularly the Asia and Pacific region, as a result of significant changes in the economic, social, demographic, and environmental trends. This quick adjustment will have a significant impact on development in ways, both well-known and obscure. Small, vulnerable, and low-income nations to larger, middle-income, and more developed knowledge-based economies in the area all face a wide range of development issues that give rise to various knowledge demands. There are still some important gaps and limitations that need to be properly addressed. Although internal CoPs play a crucial role, their individual performances have been extremely diverse. An important vacuum exists in the identification of national knowledge requirements, particularly in view of the quick changes occurring in the physical and financial environment. The monitoring of KPS

quality and implications must be improved. The collection of tacit knowledge from departing workers was one of the objectives of the KM Action Plan that was mainly not accomplished. It was also discovered that one obstacle preventing ADB from forging a competitive advantage for its KPS at the DMC level was the insufficient transmission of tacit knowledge.

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